

Changes in races of parent materials used in rice hybridizations over 10 years in Asia

Thomas R. Hargrove, associate editor, International Rice Research Institute

As part of a survey on the diffusion of genetic materials among Asian rice breeding programs, changes in the races of parents used in hybridizations were traced over a 10-year period.

Crosses were randomly selected from hybridization records at 14 experiment stations and universities in Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, Korea, Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. Genetic data were

collected on 819 parents used in 355 crosses made during 1965–67, 1970–71, and 1974–75.

Over the decade, the increasing use of semidwarf indica rices such as IR8, TN1, and their progeny largely pushed japonica, ponlai, and other races out of the breeding programs. Indicas made up 79% of the parents used in 1965–67 crosses, and 91% of those used in 1974–75 (see table). Japonicas declined in use from 11% to 4%. Although ponlais made up 6% of the 1965–67 materials, they were almost absent in 1974–75 crosses.

The project was partially funded by a research grant from The Rockefeller Foundation. ❧

Races of 819 parents used in 355 randomly selected crosses at 14 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 7 Asian nations, 1965–75.

Race of parents	Parents analyzed (%)		
	1965–67	1970–71	1974–75
Indica	79	86	91
Japonica	11	10	4
Javanica	1	1	0
Indica-japonica	1	2	4
Indica-javanica	2	<i>a</i>	0
Ponlai	6	1	<i>a</i>

^aLess than 1%.

Development and evaluation of derivatives of Mahsuri (Ponni)

P. Narayanasamy, assistant professor (rice), and S. R. Rangasamy, principal, Farm Science Center, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pondicherry 605 010, India

Mahsuri is grown on 50 to 60% of the paddy land during the monsoon season (Aug.-Sept. to Feb.) in Pondicherry state and in South Arcot, North Arcot, Chinglepet, and Tanjor districts of Tamil Nadu. Mahsuri (renamed as Ponni in this region) is popular with farmers because of its fine grain and its medium growth duration that facilitates culture in the late monsoon season.

Despite its wide use and popularity, Mahsuri lodges in heavy rain even under moderate nitrogen and is susceptible to several major insects and diseases. Therefore, an attempt at improvement was made by incorporating into it lodging resistance, high yielding ability, and field tolerance for major pests.

Mahsuri was hybridized with IR8 as the pollen parent. The F₂ through the F₆ progeny were studied. A number of medium-height derivatives and recombinants with Mahsuri-like panicles and grain types, combined with lodging resistance and increased yield potential, were developed. Thirty-seven derivatives were finally identified and compared with Mahsuri. The set was also tested in summer planting.

Mean yield data of the derivatives and the mean and range in values for a few traits are given in the table for the summer and monsoon seasons of 1977. The evaluation indicated that:

- Nine of the progeny tested were photoperiod-sensitive and did not flower when sown in the summer, even though neither parent is sensitive to photoperiod.
- The overall mean yield of the progeny grown in the summer was 77.4% higher than the mean yield in the monsoon season.
- A few of the progeny of

Mahsuri/IR8 showed recombinations of grain characteristics of Mahsuri with lodging resistance and yields higher than that of Mahsuri. The photoperiod-insensitive derivative 162/2 yielded 4.7 t/ha in the summer and 3.0 t/ha in the monsoon; 166/3 yielded 5 t/ha in the summer and 2.6 t/ha in the monsoon compared with Mahsuri's 4.3 t/ha for the summer crop and 2.5 for the monsoon crop.

- Yield tests indicated that some nonsensitive progeny can be grown in both the monsoon and summer seasons.
- The growth duration of Mahsuri and the derivatives in summer was 13 to 15 days longer than in the monsoon season.
- Derivatives that had photoperiod sensitivity gave a mean yield of 2.05 t/ha (range, 1.48 to 2.65 t/ha) – 11% lower than that of photoperiod-insensitive derivatives over two seasons. The mean yield of the insensitive derivatives was 2.31 t/ha (range, 1.41 to 3 t/ha). ❧

Mean values and range of the yield and yield components of Mahsuri (Ponni) derivatives in the summer (Feb.–June) and monsoon seasons (Sept.–Jan.) Pondicherry, India, 1977.

Yield component	Derivatives				Mahsuri (Ponni)	
	Summer		Monsoon		Summer	Monsoon
	Mean	Range	Mean	Range		
Plant ht (cm)	133.5	116.0–151.0	102.0	87.0–118	138	119
Productive tillers (no.)	7.7	4.4– 10.9	5.0	3.4– 6.7	7.4	6.4
Grains (no./panicle)	143	95.0–191.0	206	121.0–292.0	145.0	175
Length:breadth ratio of grain	2.7	2.4– 3.0	–	–	3.2	–
Yield (t/ha)	4.1	3.4– 5.0	2.3	1.4– 3.2	4.3	2.5